

Syntheses of some Substituted Arylazopyrazoles

PRAIBHA PANDEY*, SAPNA BHATTACHARYA and ARCHANA DAVE

School of Chemistry, Devi Ahilya University, Indore-452 001

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In view of the potential biological activities associated with various pyrazoles¹, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some 3-anilino-5-methyl-1-[4-(*N*-4-pyrimidinyl)sulphonamido]phenyl-4-(4-*N*-substituted-sulphonamidolphenyl)azopyrazoles (**3a-f**).

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of all the compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G plates using three different solvent systems : (a) methanol-chloroform (80 : 20), (b) ethyl acetate-xylene (20 : 80) and (c) methanol-toluene (70 : 30). Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian (270 MHz) spectrometer using (CH₃)₄Si (TMS) as an internal standard, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 160-A spectrophotometer, and mass spectra on a JN0813 X-LRP spectrometer. Elemental analyses were carried out at C.D.R.I., Lucknow.

Compounds 3a-f : An equimolar (0.005 mol) mixture of 4-hydrazino-*N*-(2-pyrimidinyl)phenylsulphonamide and 2-(4'-sulphonamoyl)phenylhydrazono-1-aminophenylbutan-1,3-dione was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) for 6 h. The colour of the reaction mixture turned orange from pale yellow. The mixture was then kept overnight at 0° and the solid thus ob-

tained was dried and crystallised from ethanol as orange needles (**3a**; 69%), m. p. 138° (Found : C, 51.48; H, 3.50; N, 20.53. C₂₉H₂₄N₁₀O₄S₃ calcd. for : C, 51.78; H, 3.57; N, 20.83%); ν_{\max} 1640 (C=N), 1585 (N=N), 1660 (C=C for phenyl ring), 750–710 cm⁻¹ (CH); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.40 (2H, CH₂), 7.25–7.75 (ArH), 8.0–8.5 (3H, pyrimidine ring); λ_{\max} 360–310 nm; *m/z* 672.

Other compounds (**3b-f**) were prepared similarly : **3b** (73%), m.p. 62°; **c** (70%), 58°; **d** (62%), 85°; **e** (59%), 100°; **f** (81%), 110°.

Antibacterial activity : All the compounds were screened *in vitro* against *Pseudomonas mongiferae*, *E. coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella aerogenes*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by the cup-plate technique in the concentration range 0.5–1.0 mg mol⁻¹. Compounds **3a** and **3d** were found active against all the bacteria except *E. coli* and compound **3c** was found active against *S. aureus* only.

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References

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